

The Noise of Scarcity: How Constant Promotions Dilute Digital Food Voucher Brands

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Abstract:

The use of digital food vouchers is becoming increasingly popular in Indonesia in line with the development of digital payments and platforms, such as Qpon, Tiktok Shop, and bankSAQU. This phenomenon is driven by Generation Z, who are heavily exposed to promotional content on social media based on discounts, flash sales, or limited offers. In practice, marketing strategies that rely on scarcity and high promotion frequency are a common pattern used in the digital food voucher sector. Although such strategies effectively increase transactional activity in the short term, academic research has not sufficiently examined their long-term effects on brand equity. This research investigates the impact of scarcity marketing and promotion frequency on brand dilution, where perceived monetary value is proposed as a mediator. An online survey was conducted among 120 respondents in the Greater Jakarta (Jabodetabek) area who had experience using or redeeming digital food vouchers. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The results indicate that the frequency of promotions significantly decreases perceived monetary worth, while the scarcity marketing approach no longer improves value perception. Both factors directly hasten brand dilution without significant mediation. We demonstrate the danger of overdependence on promotional tactics and suggest implications for sustainable brand management.

Keyword: scarcity marketing, brand dilution, perceived monetary value, digital food voucher, social commerce

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to mobile payments usage and the growth of social commerce platforms, especially in the food voucher sector, promotions with time or quantity restrictions are quickly expanding in Indonesia's digital economy. According to the trends, popular applications like TikTok, Qpon & bankSAQU run flash sale, limited coupon and countdown regularly. This phenomenon is a manifestation of the scarcity principle, where time constraints or availability are used to create a sense of urgency that often leads to impulsive buying (Barton et al., 2022).

Redseer Southeast Asia predicts that the Indonesian digital voucher market is projected to register at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of about 14% by 2030 (TMT News, 2025). The presence of Generation Z, which dominates the digital market, is the main driver of this growth. By 2025 the national gift card and incentive market is forecasted to reach approximately USD 2.4 billion, indicating that interest

in voucher-based products remains strong. Meanwhile, GMV at TikTok Shop has grown rapidly, making Indonesia one of the most active markets for scarcity-driven marketing approach.

Behind positive market signals, the use of scarcity signals and price promotions can also have potential long-term consequences. A company's image and perception of quality can even be damaged if customers constantly rely on special offers, where they will continuously expect lower prices than normal. When companies reduce discount promotions and shift to stable pricing strategies, consumers who have become accustomed to discounts feel they are losing value, leading to a decline in sales (Reidel, 2023). Similarly, research on regular promotional events such as Black Friday and Boxing Day sales shows that when discounts are offered too often, customers become skeptical of the promised value (Barrett, 2024; Jackson, 2024).

Frequent promotions as well as scarcity cues may affect consumers attitudes about monetary value. When discounts become more frequent, consumers may begin to perceive the brand as a discount provider and disregard its value. This shift may expedite brand dilution, characterized by a loss in perceived quality, dilution of association with the brand and reliance on price (Bacchiega et al., 2024). Beyond promotional tactics, brand dilution has been studied as a negative result of brand equity exploitation, especially when brand extensions are not executed strategically. Brand extensions allow companies to capitalize on a strong image, but can have adverse effects if they deviate from the core brand positioning (Keller & Aaker, 1992; Loken & John, 1993). Scarcity and price promotions are indirect brand extension efforts, which are known to be effective in boosting sales in a short period of time. This strategy is often repeated and controlled by the platform, causing companies to lose control over their brand message.

Consumers of digital food vouchers in Indonesia, especially those who are highly dependent on social commerce platforms, are the focus of this study. As a digital natives, they are often exposed to scarcity signals such as “last chance,” “only a few left,” and so on. They encounter such promotional claims repeatedly, which shape their purchase evaluations and expectations. This study examines how scarcity strategies and promotion frequency influence consumers' perceptions of monetary value, which in turn impacts brand equity. The conceptual framework is based on perceived value theory and brand equity theory, which together explain how consumers assess the benefits obtained compared to the costs incurred, as well as how poorly executed promotional practices can damage a brand's image. This study has three main objectives: (1) examine the impact of scarcity strategies on consumers' perceptions of monetary value; (2) analyze the influence of promotion frequency on consumer price expectations; and (3) investigate the role of perceived monetary value as a mediating variable in explaining the relationship between scarcity-based promotion strategies and brand value erosion in the context of digital voucher consumption in Indonesian social commerce.

Despite earlier research on scarcity marketing's short-term efficacy, there are still a number of gaps. First, long-term brand-related outcomes such as brand dilution still understudied. Second, there has not been much empirical research on the mediating function of perceived monetary worth between marketing approaches and brand dilution. Third, the Indonesian environment of digital food vouchers, which is

characterized by significant advertising and social commerce dynamics, has not received enough attention. To address these gaps, this study examines how perceived monetary value mediates the direct and indirect effects of scarcity marketing and promotion frequency on brand dilution.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Scarcity Marketing and Perceived Monetary Value

Scarcity marketing refers to tactics that intentionally restrict a product's availability in terms of time, quantity or access to create urgency and exclusivity (B, 2025; Goetha et al., 2024). Scarcity appeals are typically provided by presenting flash sales, low-stock messages or limited time offers that generate competitive arousal among consumers, that hasten consumer decision-making (Wulandjani et al., 2023; Broeder & Wentink, 2022). The scarcity created triggers consumers' justification of prices, with perceived monetary value being a key result. Perceived monetary value consumers' assessment of whether costs are worth benefits were comprised, which include price fairness, monetary gains from discounts, and utility relative to sacrifice (Huang et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024). Scarcity cues in digital vouchers raise sensitivity to discounts, restrictions, and deadlines. However, recent studies highlight that this relationship is not strictly linear. Wulandjani et al., (2023) identify an inverted U-shaped effect, whereby scarcity initially increases perceived value but then decreases when scarcity cues become excessive or untrustworthy.

H1: Scarcity Marketing has a significant positive effect on Perceived Monetary Value.

2.2 Promotion Frequency and Perceived Monetary Value

Promotion frequency reflects the regularity of price-based strategies, which boosts exposure to discounts and modifies consumer perceptions of product availability and appeal (Wulandjani et al., 2023). This heightens awareness of discount strength, familiarity with patterns, and adjustments to internal reference prices (Gardner, 2022; Jing et al., 2022; Wamsler et al., 2024). Frequent advertising in digital voucher environments, where discounts, redemption restrictions, and timing cues are very prominent, has a significant impact on consumer evaluations and behavior (Haslina et al., 2024; Lamei et al., 2025; Permadi & Ghoni, 2024; Putriyandari et al., n.d.). Promotion frequency negatively affects perceived monetary value by normalizes discounts, gaining perceived price advantage, and eroding utility value (Bacchiega et al., 2024; McRae & Dubé, 2024). This variable is chosen for its prevalence in competitive digital markets, where habitual exposure shifts consumer norms. This study closes the knowledge gap on the erosion effects of frequency in Indonesia's voucher ecosystem, which is frequently overrun with obvious promotions.

H2: Promotion Frequency has a significant negative effect on Perceived Monetary Value.

2.3 Perceived Monetary Value and Brand Dilution

Brand dilution is the term used to describe this erosion of brand associations because of over-exposure or inconsistent marketing (Bacchiega et al., 2024; Christou et al., 2025; Li, 2025). Customers reveal a higher price sensitivity and dependence as the discounted prices become the norm, which leads to risks of brand dilution because of decreased loyalty, weakened differentiation, and decreased perceived quality (Kanwal, 2025; Kučinskis, 2024). In this situation, consumers become less loyal to brands, as they are willing to switch brands for more favorable promotional alternatives. Thus, a brand is no longer viewed for its uniqueness, blurring the differences between competing brands. Perceived monetary value mediates this by weighing financial benefits against costs. While discounts temporarily elevate value, prolonged exposure shifts focus on transactions, reducing exclusivity (Lie et al., 2024). Brand dilution negativity correlates with perceived monetary value where the lower is the value, the faster erosion will run. Selected for its explanatory strength in associating promotions with long-term equity, this key factor captures the void on why perceived value motivates dilution in Indonesia's voucher market even when short-term dominance is achieved at the expense of longer-run stake.

H3: Perceived Monetary Value has a significant negative effect on Brand Dilution.

2.4 Direct Effects of Scarcity Marketing and Promotion Frequency on Brand Dilution

Scarcity marketing directly fosters brand dilution through skepticism and reactance from perceived artificial shortages, harming attitudes even without value changes (Goetha et al., 2024; Ye et al., 2024). Customers may start to associate a brand with discounts rather than its true value if price promotions are offered without a clear strategic purpose. Recent evidence shows that unplanned and repetitive discount promotions can damage brand image, reduce perceived brand value, and encourage brand switching behavior (Kanwal, 2025). Brand uniqueness and long-term brand equity are further diminished in highly competitive digital marketplaces by predictable and continuous promotions.

H4a: Scarcity Marketing has a significant direct effect on Brand Dilution.

H4b: Promotion Frequency has a significant direct effect on Brand Dilution.

2.5 Impact of Proposed Mediating Variable

Perceived monetary value is positioned as a mediating variable, not merely as an assessment of whether a product is cheap or expensive, but as a way for consumers to interpret a series of promotional signals. In current digital market, where consumers prefer to assess prices, perceived monetary value here acts as an evaluative lens that determines whether a brand is still "worth the money" at its normal price. (Huang et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2025). This perceived monetary value is an early sign of a shift in consumer perspective, before a more profound change in brand image occurs. This research incorporates both direct and indirect routes in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of how scarcity marketing and

promotional frequency impact brand dilution and perceived monetary worth in Indonesia's digital voucher ecosystem.

H5a: Scarcity Marketing has a significant effect on Brand Dilution through the mediation of Perceived Monetary Value.

H5b: Promotion Frequency has a significant effect on Brand Dilution through the mediation of Perceived Monetary Value.

Figure 1. Research Model

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative research design with a causal-explanatory approach to examine predetermined hypotheses and explore the relationship between variables. The main objective is to measure the impact of Scarcity Marketing and Promotion Frequency (independent variable) on Brand Dilution (dependent variable), mediated by Perceived Monetary Value. This analysis targets young individuals, particularly those aged 18-35 who actively use digital food voucher platforms in the Greater Jakarta area (Jabodetabek).

Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) was the chosen statistical technique for its robustness in handling complex models and non-normal data distributions (Yunara & Novia, 2025). The minimum number of respondents expected was 100 to ensure adequate statistical power. Data was collected through an online survey, presenting 16 statements in accordance with the indicators and using a Likert scale for responses. The operational definitions and measurement indicators for each variable used in this study are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Operational definition and indicators of research variables

Variable	Operational Definitions	Indicators	Adapted Measurement
Scarcity marketing (B, 2025; Goetha et al., 2024; Wulandjani et al., 2023)	Scarcity marketing refers to a strategy that limits product availability through limitations in time, quantity, or access in order to create a sense of urgency and perceived exclusivity among consumers.	<i>Time-limited scarcity</i>	SM1. I often encounter digital food vouchers that are only available for a very short period (e.g., within hours or minutes).
		<i>Quantitative scarcity</i>	SM2. The digital food/beverage vouchers I purchase often have limited quotas per person or per day, indicated by a "low stock" label.
		<i>Competitive arousal</i>	SM3. These limitations create a sense of competition with other buyers to avoid missing out.
		<i>Scarcity skepticism</i>	SM4. I consider "limited stock" claims to be a strategy used to encourage consumers to buy immediately.
Promotion frequency (Gardner, 2022; Wulandjani et al., 2023; Jing et al., 2022; Wamsler et al., 2024)	Promotion frequency refers to how regularly and intensively a brand or platform offers price-based promotions (discounts, coupons, flash sales) within a specific period. This construct captures not only the number of promotional occurrences, but also the consistency and predictability of promotional patterns over time.	<i>Promotion intensity</i>	PF1. The shopping platforms/brands I use very frequently offer discount vouchers (e.g., flash sale offers multiple times a week).
		<i>Promotion regularity</i>	PF2. These food voucher discount promotions are held regularly (e.g., every week or every month).
		<i>Promotion familiarity</i>	PF3. I am very familiar with the discount patterns, so I tend to wait for promotional periods rather than buying at normal prices.
		<i>Price normalization</i>	PF4. The normal price (without a discount voucher) for these products now feels too expensive to me.

Perceived monetary value (Huang et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2025)	Perceived monetary value is defined as the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received (benefits) versus what is given (price).	<i>Price fairness</i>	PMV1. The final price (after the discount voucher) that I pay feels very reasonable given the quality of the food/beverage product I receive.
		<i>Perceived monetary gain</i>	PMV2. I feel that I have achieved significant financial savings compared to if I had purchased the product without a voucher.
		<i>Utility value</i>	PMV3. These discount vouchers provide the best value for the money I spend.
Brand dilution (Bacchiega et al., 2024; Christou et al., 2025; Li, 2025)	Brand dilution refers to the gradual weakening of brand associations, quality perceptions, and exclusivity due to inconsistent or excessive promotional strategies.	<i>Weakened brand association</i>	BD1. I tend to perceive brands that too frequently offer large discount vouchers as brands that focus on low prices rather than quality.
		<i>Decreased perception of quality</i>	BD2. The frequency of large discount promotions leads me to assume that the brand is struggling to sell its products.
		<i>Decreased brand loyalty</i>	BD3. I would not hesitate to switch to a competitor if they offer a more favorable discount voucher.
		<i>Loss of exclusivity</i>	BD4. The brand no longer feels exclusive because it holds discount promotions too often.
		<i>Price dependency</i>	BD5. I would likely stop buying this brand's products if the discount vouchers were completely removed.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study surveyed 120 participants, the majority of whom were aged 18-35 years old, consisting of 57.5% female and 42.5% male participants. All respondents had experience using digital food and

beverage vouchers through platforms such as food delivery applications (35.83%), followed by e-commerce platforms (29.17%), and voucher or financial platforms (23.33%). Data evidence related to data collection can also be accessed through the [link](#).

Table 2. Respondent Profile

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
< 18	9	7.5
18 - 25	44	36.7
26 - 35	29	24.2
36 - 45	23	19.2
> 45	15	12.5
Gender		
Male	51	42.5
Female	69	57.5
Factors Influencing Purchase Decision		
Attractive Price	63	52.5
Food Quality	58	48.3
Promotion	52	43.3
Brand Trust	51	42.5
Positive Reviews	47	39.2
Ease of Transaction and Delivery	32	26.7
Voucher Usage Frequency		
1 - 2 times	21	17.5
3 - 5 times	46	38.3
6 - 10 times	38	31.7
More than 10 times	15	12.5
Main Platforms for Digital Voucher Usage		
Food delivery applications	49	40.8
E-commerce platforms	42	35
Voucher or financial platforms	34	28.3

These results prove that the use of digital food vouchers is quite common among Generation Z and Generation Y in Jabodetabek. The collected data was analyzed using SEM-PLS with SmartPLS 3.0 software, conducted in two main stages: evaluating the outer and inner models. The outer model measures variables

for convergent validity, construct validity, and reliability. The inner model focuses on estimating the connections between the latent variables.

Table 3. Reliability And Validity Results

Variable	Composite Reliability	AVE
Scarcity Marketing	0.837	0.562
Promotion Frequency	0.856	0.599
Perceived Monetary Value	0.960	0.888
Brand Dilution	0.877	0.589

As presented in **Table 3**, all constructs demonstrate satisfactory internal consistency and convergent validity. Composite Reliability (CR) values vary between 0.837 and 0.960 being all higher than the suggested threshold of 0.70, while all Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are greater than 0.50. These results indicate that the measurement items explain the variance in the indicators and accurately capture the corresponding latent constructs. This outcome aligns to SEM-PLS guidelines, which emphasize CR and AVE as key indicators of construct reliability and validity in behavioral research.

Table 4. R-Square Results

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Perceived Monetary Value	0.080	0.064
Brand Dilution	0.472	0.458

In **Table 4**, results from the structural model reveal that Scarcity Marketing and Promotion Frequency account for a relatively low level of variance in Perceived Monetary Value ($R^2 = 0.080$) suggesting weak predictability. In comparison the model has moderate explanatory power in Brand Dilution ($R^2 = 0.472$). This asymmetry implies that while perceived monetary value is influenced by additional factors beyond promotional strategies, brand dilution is substantially driven by repeated exposure to scarcity cues and high promotion frequency. Similar patterns have been found in recent branding research where the effect of promotional intensity on brand equity depreciation proved to be more direct than its one contemporaneous short-term value perception (Bacchiega et al., 2024; Kučinskas, 2024).

Table 5. Hypothesis Results

Variable	T Statistics	P Values	Details
SM → PMV	1.574	0.116	H1 Rejected
PF → PMV	3.098	0.002	H2 Approved
PMV → BD	1.546	0.123	H3 Rejected
SM → BD	5.781	0.000	H4a Approved
PF → BD	5.977	0.000	H4b Approved

SM → PMV → BD	0.996	0.320	H5a Rejected
PF → PMV → BD	1.303	0.203	H5b Rejected

Based on the results presented in **Table 5**, three hypotheses demonstrate significant influence, as indicated by a t-statistic value > 1.96 and a P-value < 0.05 . However, four hypotheses are rejected, with a t-statistic value < 1.96 and a P-value > 0.05 . These results suggest that not all promotion mechanisms work in the same way on perceived value and brand outcomes within the online food voucher context.

The relationship between scarcity marketing and perceived monetary value is statistically insignificant ($t = 1.574$; $p = 0.116$), leading to the rejection of H1. Contrary to previous findings that explain that scarcity strategies can legitimize prices and increase perceived value (Goetha et al., 2024; Wulandjani et al., 2023), this study shows that Gen Z audiences in Jabodetabek tend to be more rational towards scarcity claims. Scarcity promotions are no longer perceived as an exclusive value but rather as part of routine, predictable marketing tactics.

In contrast, promotion frequency significantly affects perceived monetary value ($t = 3.098$; $p = 0.002$), supporting H2. The result suggests that repeated exposure to discounts causes consumers to reset their mental price standards. Promotional prices, which should be a special benefit, are slowly considered a reasonable or normal price reference. When the product is sold without a promotion, Gen Z's interest in the product decreases because they expect a discount (Gardner, 2022; McRae & Dubé, 2024). Some of them may even choose to switch to competing brands.

The effect of perceived monetary value on brand dilution is not significant ($t = 1.546$; $p = 0.123$) which leads to the rejection of H3. This shows that Gen Z's perception of monetary value does not affect brand value. Even when consumers consider the use of vouchers to be a saving, this perception is not strong enough to protect the brand from a decline in image, supporting recent arguments that symbolic brand meaning erodes faster than value perceptions in promotion-saturated markets (Bacchiaga et al., 2024; Lie et al., 2024).

Both scarcity marketing ($t = 5.781$; $p = 0.000$) and promotion frequency ($t = 5.977$; $p = 0.000$) have a significant direct influence on brand dilution, supporting H4a and H4b. These results indicate that excessive use of scarcity cues and frequent discount promotions directly accelerate brand dilution by increasing consumer skepticism, reducing perceived quality, and strengthening price dependency. These findings are consistent with brand equity literature, which shows that consumer dependence on promotions makes consumers increasingly reliant on low prices as the main reason for making purchases (Lalwani et al., 2021; Kanwal, 2025; Kučinskis, 2024). However, the indirect effect of promotional strategies on brand erosion was not found to be significant, as indicated by the results of H5a ($t = 0.996$; $p = 0.320$) and H5b ($t = 1.303$; $p = 0.203$). This proves that perceived monetary value does not play an effective role as a mediating variable.

5. CONCLUSION

This study provides insight into the factors that influence the decline in brand value, particularly in the digital voucher sector. According to the results of the study, excessive use of scarcity strategies and overly

frequent promotions can indeed stimulate sales in the short term. However, these strategies do not always make consumers feel that the product is more valuable. This is especially true for Generation Z, who are accustomed to discounts. They have begun to view promotions as nothing special, but rather as a routine practice. Some of them even doubt the “limited” claims, suspecting them to be just a marketing ploy.

The results of this study show that both scarcity strategies and promotional frequency have been proven to directly reduce brand value. Over-reliance on promotions makes brands more often associated with low prices, so that uniqueness, quality, and brand image are slowly beginning to be ignored. Promotions that were originally intended for brand expansion have the potential to damage brand equity through the uncontrolled application of promotional strategies.

From a managerial perspective, providers of digital promotions or vouchers need to be more prudent in regulating how often and how intensely they are used. The implementation of promotional strategies must be balanced with brand image building strategies that emphasize quality, differentiation, and trust for sustained brand equity. However, this study is limited by its sample size and cross-sectional design. Future research may explore longitudinal effects, broader consumer segments, as well as more psychological dimensions to explore whether there will be lasting impacts of promotion-saturated digital markets.

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